

ISic1292

I.Sicily inscription 1292

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 309

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. []να άν
2. [δριζ]ήσαντι
3. [ἔτη] με' Γρα
4. [πτ]η σύμβιο[ς]
5. [έ]ποίησ[εν]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

for [an unnamed] man, who lived for 45 years. Built by his partner, Grapte.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492896

EDCS 39101661

PHI 140782

PHI 316220

Bibliography

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- Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 92
- Ferrua, A 1941. Epigrafica sicula pagana e cristiana. *Rivista di archeologia cristiana*. 18: 151-243. At 179 no.42

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